

Energy Versus Internal Energy and a Lorentz Boost of an Ideal Gas

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We argue that in thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, energy and internal energy are not equivalent. It seems that internal energy is associated with a rest frame of an ideal gas system, even though a Lorentz boost does not discriminate between the two. In particular, internal energy appears in the Sackur-Tetrode formula for entropy and entropy is linked to a physical counting of states. Thus, a special energy, namely internal energy, is associated with the Sackur-Tetrode formula.

We suggest that a problem arises when one Lorentz boosts an ideal gas because energy \rightarrow $g(v)$ energy, where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but $g(v)$ internal energy is no longer strictly internal energy. It is a combination of internal energy and collective motion energy. Thus, it seems that an equation which applies to internal energy should not really be used with a new energy which is not strictly speaking internal. For example, in (1), $P dV$ is taken to transform as energy i.e. $g(v)$ energy, dV as $dV/g(v)$ so P transforms as $g(v)g(v) P$. We argue, however, that P , like internal energy, is based on special conditions and that objects like $g(v)g(v) P$ and $g(v) T$, where T is temperature, no longer represent purely statistical objects. Furthermore, if one transforms variables such as internal energy, V and rest m , one finds that the entropy value of the Sackur-Tetrode entropy divided by k (Boltzmann constant) changes which should not happen if it represents $\ln(\text{number of states})$. This seems to lead to the conclusion that thermodynamic quantities like T , entropy etc apply to a system with bias removed (if possible). A moving frame is a biased frame and so we suggest that one perform thermodynamic/statistical mechanical equations in the rest frame.

Thermodynamics/Statistical Mechanics Versus Lorentz Boosts

Lorentz boosts usually do not discriminate between types of energy used as the fourth component of (momentum, energy). One may use thermal energy, rest mass energy or potential energy, for example. An exception is electromagnetic field energy: $\int dv (.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B)$, where E is the electric field and B , the magnetic.

Thermodynamics/statistical mechanics, on the other hand, focus on distributable energy with as much bias being removed as possible (i.e. a maximum number of states or entropy). Thus, not all energy is available for non-biased distribution and one cannot use any energy value in an equation requiring internal energy.. For example, if a gas is moving, there is kinetic energy associated with motion, which is not considered non-biased energy that may be distributed among particles in a statistical manner which maximizes entropy (i.e. minimizes bias). Thus, in thermodynamics, one speaks of internal energy as the non-biased energy.

We argue that issues arise when one considers Lorentz boosts of thermodynamics quantities and internal energy because what is non-biased energy in a rest frame becomes a combination of biased and motion energy as seen from a frame watching the moving gas. Thus, in a rest frame, for a nonrelativistic case, one has internal energy = $1.5 nRT$ and this transforms as $g(v) 1.5 nRT$, where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but this transformed energy is a combination of motion energy and thermal (nonbiased energy). Equations which apply to statistical

mechanics/thermodynamics in a rest frame seem to be used for a moving gas and Lorentz transformations applied to variables which changes them into non-statistical ones. As a result, purely statistical quantities now become a combination of statistical and systematic (collective) quantities, which seems to break the sense of thermodynamics/statistical mechanics. As a specific example, we consider the effects on the Sackur-Tetrode equation for entropy.

Sackur-Tetrode Equation for Entropy

Boltzmann entropy is defined as (1): $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$ ((1))

The number of states is based on distributable energy. If one has a set of particles which all have the same velocity, there is one state (no entropy), even though this may represent a large overall energy. In other words, one has collective energy, not internal energy, i.e. the energy is not distributable in a non-biased manner (maximum entropy manner).

The Sackur-Tetrode equation describes the entropy of an ideal gas, i.e. one which obeys:

$PV = nRT$ where P is pressure, V volume and T temperature ((2))

The Sackur-Tetrode equation is: $S/(kN) = 5/2 + \ln(\{V/N\} [4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot m_0 U / (3hN)]^{1.5})$ ((3))

Here U is internal energy, not just any energy, we argue.

If one simply considers a Lorentz boost, then:

$V \rightarrow V/g(v)$, $U \rightarrow g(v)U$ and $m_0 \rightarrow g(v) m_0$ ((3))

$S/(k)$ is proportional to the number of states, a physical quantity which is not changed by constant motion of the system. Yet, if one uses the transformed quantities ((3)) and retains the Sackur-Tetrode equation then:

$S/k \rightarrow \ln(g(v)g(v) + S(\text{non-boost})$ ((4))

S/k , however, represents $\ln(\text{number of states})$ and this should be a Lorentz invariant, so it seems there is a problem if one uses transformed boost variable ((3)) which do not belong in the Sackur-Tetrode equation because they do not represent internal energy (for example) which is fully distributable in a non-biased manner (max-entropy manner) among the particles. The problem is that the boost is associated with a collective parameter v in one direction, and this is not statistical (i.e. it is biased and can be removed by going into the lab frame). Thus, we suggest that thermodynamical/statistical mechanical equations should be evaluated in a rest frame, and care should be taken when considering Lorentz boosts of such variables.

Lorentz Boosts of Statistical Quantities

As an example, we considered Lorentz boosts of quantities ((3)), where U , internal energy, is a statistical quantity. We now consider an example from (3). In (3), it is argued that: PdV is like energy and should transform overall as $g(v) P dV$. $dV \rightarrow dV/g(v)$ so P =pressure transforms as $g(v) g(v) P$. Temperature T transforms as $g(v)T$. We argue that P and T are statistical quantities and it might be best to consider their values in the rest frame. For example, thermal energy is due to motion in all directions, not to biased unidirectional motion. In Newtonian mechanics, a mass that is moving has energy $mv^2/2$, but also collective momentum mv . Thermal energy $3/2 nRT$ in the rest mass (nonrelativistic treatment) represents a $3/2 kT$ energy in the boosted frame, but there is also a momentum in one direction which should not be present for a statistical quantity. This is collective motion energy. T , temperature, should measure internal statistical energy, we argue. Thus, we suggest considering Lorentz boosted statistical quantities with caution.

Conclusion

Lorentz boosts seldom discriminate among energies which may be boosted, e.g. rest mass, thermal, potential etc. (Electromagnetic field energy is an exception.) Thermodynamics/statistical mechanics, however, deals with a special type of energy called internal energy. This energy may be distributed among particles in the least biased way possible, hence maximizing the possible number of states (and also the entropy). Not all energy types, however, may be distributed in such a manner. For example, collective energy of a moving gas is not available as thermal energy. Thus, the strange situation is that a Lorentz boost takes a purely internal energy U and converts it into $g(v)U$ which is a combination of internal energy and collective motion energy. Thus, we argue that this quantity cannot simply be used in thermodynamical/statistical mechanical equations which require a pure internal energy. We cite the Sackur-Tetrode entropy equation for an ideal gas as an example. $S = k \ln(\text{number of states})$, but transforming variables in the Sackur-Tetrode equation according to Lorentz boost rules leads to a different $S/k = \ln(\text{number of states})$ which should not be. The problem may be resolved by requiring that internal energy be used, but this means that one calculates variables in a rest frame, i.e. a frame which removes as much bias as possible. Thus, one cannot really use boosted values as if they were statistical ones and caution should be exercised. If one sees $T \rightarrow g(v)T$, $g(v)T$ is no longer linked only to statistical internal energy, but is a combination of internal energy and collective motion energy, we argue.

References

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